

FORMING THE ECOLOGICAL CULTURE OF FUTURE TEACHERS ON THE BASIS OF THE HERITAGE OF EASTERN THINKERS

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Abstract. The issues of forming an ecological culture in future teachers are covered based on the views of Eastern thinkers on the harmony between nature, man and society. The pedagogical importance of educating the younger generation in the spirit of a responsible attitude to nature in the context of the globalization of environmental problems is analyzed.

Also, the theoretical and practical aspects of using the heritage of Eastern scholars in the educational process are considered.

Keywords: ecological culture, Eastern thinkers, ecological education, future teacher, spiritual heritage, nature, ecological consciousness, sustainable development.

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ НА ОСНОВЕ НАСЛЕДИЯ ВОСТОЧНЫХ МЫСЛИТЕЛЕЙ

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются вопросы формирования экологической культуры у будущих учителей на основе взглядов восточных мыслителей на гармонию между природой, человеком и обществом.

Анализируется педагогическая значимость воспитания молодого поколения в духе ответственного отношения к природе в контексте глобализации экологических проблем.

Также рассматриваются теоретические и практические аспекты использования наследия восточных ученых в образовательном процессе.

Ключевые слова: экологическая культура, восточные мыслители, экологическое образование, будущий учитель, духовное наследие, природа, экологическое сознание, устойчивое развитие.

SHARQ MUTAFAKKIRLARI MEROSI ASOSIDA BO'LAJAK O'QITUVCHILARNING EKOLOGIK MADANIYATINI SHAKLLANTIRISH

Annotatsiya. Sharq mutafakkirlarining tabiat, inson va jamiyat o'rtasidagi uyg'unlik haqidagi qarashlari asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda ekologik madaniyatni shakllantirish masalalari yoritilgan.

Ekologik muammolarning globallasuvi sharoitida yosh avlodni tabiatga mas'uliyatli munosabat ruhida tarbiyalashning pedagogik ahamiyati tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, Sharq allomalari merosidan ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonida foydalanishning nazariy va amaliy jihatlari ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ekologik madaniyat, Sharq mutafakkirlari, ekologik tarbiya, bo'lajak o'qituvchi, ma'naviy meros, tabiat, ekologik ong, barqaror rivojlanish.

Introduction

One of the most urgent problems facing humanity today is environmental problems.

Problems such as global climate change, atmospheric pollution, depletion of water resources, desertification and loss of biodiversity require a reconsideration of the relationship between man and nature. Therefore, the formation of ecological culture is recognized as one of the priority areas of modern education. Ecological culture is a concept that expresses a conscious, responsible and careful attitude of man to nature. It is manifested in the harmony of ecological knowledge, values, moral standards and practical activities. The formation of ecological culture in future teachers is especially important. Because a teacher is not only a person who gives knowledge, but also educates the younger generation and sets an example for them.

Eastern thinkers in their works paid special attention to the issues of harmony between man and nature, environmental protection, rational use of natural resources and spiritual purity. Their rich scientific and spiritual heritage serves as an important source for enriching the content of ecological education.

Ecological ideas in the heritage of Eastern thinkers: The issues of respect for nature, its preservation and care occupy an important place in the works of Eastern scholars. They emphasized that human coexistence with nature is one of the main factors of social development.

Abu Nasr Al-Farabi noted that the disruption of the balance between man and nature has a negative impact on the development of society. He considered nature as an integral part of human life.

Abu Rayhan Al-Biruni conducted many studies in geography, biology and ecology in his scientific work. He is one of the scientists who scientifically substantiated the need for rational use of natural resources.

Abu Ali ibn Sino paid special attention to the connection between human health and the environment. His works widely covered the importance of clean air, water and a healthy natural environment in human life. The ideas of the beauty of nature, its appreciation and preservation also occupy an important place in the work of Alisher Navoi. The poet interpreted nature as an integral part of human spirituality.

Pedagogical foundations of the formation of ecological culture in future teachers: The formation of ecological culture is one of the important tasks of the continuous education system.

Students studying in pedagogical higher educational institutions will actively participate in the development of the ecological consciousness of society in the future. Ecological culture in future teachers consists of 5 components, which are: ecological knowledge; ecological thinking; ecological values; ecological responsibility; ecological activity skills. The harmonious development of these components forms the ecological competence of students.

Possibilities of using the heritage of Eastern thinkers in the educational process: The use of the ecological views of Eastern thinkers in the educational process serves to develop the ecological worldview of young people.

In addition, it is of great importance to include examples of the works of scientists in the educational process, introduce spiritual and educational events of ecological content, hold scientific conferences and round tables, launch project and research activities, and organize ecological excursions.

Ecological culture and sustainable development: Today, the concept of sustainable development is one of the important directions in solving environmental problems. The Sustainable Development Goals put forward by the United Nations pay special attention to environmental education.

Educators with an ecological culture take a responsible approach to nature protection, actively participate in the ecological education of young people, help implement ecological projects, and contribute to the development of ecological awareness in society.

In this regard, the heritage of Eastern thinkers is a key element of modern environmental education. Modern environmental problems and the tasks of the educator: The environmental problems of the 21st century are placing new demands on the education system. Now the educator must be not only a provider of knowledge, but also a propagator of ecological culture.

Future teachers must know the issues of environmental safety, master the methods of ecological education, participate in ecological projects, and support initiatives to preserve nature.

In implementing these tasks, the heritage of Eastern scholars serves as an important methodological resource.

In conclusion, the rich scientific and spiritual heritage of Eastern thinkers is one of the important sources for the formation of ecological culture in future teachers.

The views on nature of such scholars as Farobiy, Beruniy, Ibn Sino, Navoiy have not lost their significance in solving today's environmental problems.

The development of ecological culture in future educators requires not only the acquisition of ecological knowledge, but also the formation of a responsible attitude towards nature, ecological thinking, and ecological values.

Effective use of the heritage of Eastern thinkers in the educational process serves to develop the ecological consciousness of the younger generation.

Ecologically cultured educators will play an important role in preventing environmental problems, protecting the environment and implementing the goals of sustainable development in the future.

Therefore, the system of training pedagogical personnel is to improve environmental education based on the heritage of Eastern scholars.

As a result, the opportunity to train educators who are environmentally responsible, spiritually mature and have a modern worldview will expand.

This will serve the ecologically sustainable development of society and the prosperous life of the future generation.

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